

SEPARATION OF METHYL ESTERS OF FATTY ACIDS FROM THEIR MIXTURES BY UREA COMPLEXES

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The separation of saturated and unsaturated acids from their mixtures by the urea-complex procedure is only of a qualitative nature and cannot be adopted as an analytical method.

Schlenk and Holman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 5001) from their study on the urea-complex formation of binary mixtures of some fatty acids in methyl alcohol at 25° found that the separation was better when the difference in unsaturation and chain-length of the constituents was more, but separation into pure acids was not possible in any case. It was considered worthwhile to try the separation of the constituents of the binary mixtures of some common methyl esters of fatty acids using urea solutions in methyl alcohol of different concentrations and quantities and by fractional separation of urea complexes formed by the addition of urea in two or more stages.

EXPERIMENTAL

As the esters were found to furnish increased yields of urea complexes than the free fatty acids, methyl esters of the various acids having the following constants were employed in these experiments: stearic, m. p. 69°, M.W. 283.5; palmitic, m.p. 61.5°, M. W. 257; oleic, I. V. 87; linoleic, I. V. 187.

The mixtures of the acid esters were prepared by mixing equal quantities of the esters of two acids, one of them being saturated and the other unsaturated acid. The mixtures of acid esters were treated under various conditions with urea at 15°. After keeping overnight, each mixture was filtered through a sintered glass funnel and the crystals of the complexes were washed with petroleum ether (b. p. 40°-60°). The complexes were decomposed with HCl (dil., 1%). The separated fatty acids were recovered with petroleum ether (40°-60°) and isolated as usual. The solvents were completely removed from the raffinate and the washings, and after acidifying with HCl (dil.) the fatty acids were isolated as above. The amount of component esters in each fraction was calculated from its iodine value. The results with the mixtures of linoleic and stearic acid esters (1:1) are shown in Table I.

The solid urea complexes (1 g.), obtained from experiment 1 (Table I), were recrystallised from methyl alcohol (15 c.c.). After keeping overnight at 15°, the esters were isolated from the separated crystals; yield 59.5% on the total mixture (I. V. 28.3) affording the linoleic ester in the fraction as 16.4%. Recrystallisation of the above complexes lowered the yield of the esters in solid material to 36%, but the linoleic ester content was only 5.7%. When methyl alcohol, saturated with urea, was used for crystallisation of the solid complexes, the iodine value of the esters obtained from the crystallised product could not be at all reduced.

TABLE I

Separation of the components from the mixture of linoleic and stearic acid esters (1:1) by urea complexes.

No.	Urea (g.) and MeOH (c.c. per g. of the ester mixture).	Esters in complexes			Esters in raffinate.		
		Amount.	I. V. (Wijs).	Linoleic ester in the fraction.	Amount.	I. V. (Wijs).	Linoleic ester in the fraction.
1	12 in saturated solution *	74.33%	56.9	33.0%	24.52%	166.2	95.4%
2	3 " "	60.06	35.7	20.7	38.72	160.0	93.0
3	2.1 " "	48.26	28.4	16.4	0.46	156.3	90.6
4	12 in 80% MeOH saturated soln.	79.9	77.9	45.0	15.47	100.0	58.0
5	Urea : MeOH, 5 : 7	89.0	75.7	43.9	9.48	161.2	93.5

* The saturated solution was prepared at room temperature (28° - 32°) and contained about 20% urea, so the ratio of urea to MeOH was approximately 1 : 5 in the solution.

The urea complexes obtained from saturated methyl alcohol (about 20% urea conc.) with some binary mixtures of saturated and unsaturated acid esters (1 g.) were recrystallised from methyl alcohol (10 c.c.). The characteristics of the esters obtained from the solid product are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Composition of ester fractions from urea complexes of acid mixtures after crystallisation from methyl alcohol.

No.	Component of ester mixture	Urea added per g. of the ester mixtures in sat. soln.	Esters in crystallised complexes.		
			Amount.	I. V. (Wijs).	Unsaturated ester content in the fraction.
1	Stearic-linoleic (1:1)	12 g.	71.2%	50.1	29.0%
2	Palmitic-linoleic (1:1)	12	70.8	55.3	32.1
3	Palmitic-oleic (1:1)	12	72.4	37.2	43.5

Fractionation of Esters by addition of Urea in stages.—To 1 g. of the fatty acid ester mixture urea (2 g.) in methyl alcohol, just enough to make a saturated solution, was added. After keeping overnight at 15° the solid complexes (C_1) were removed and 2 g. of more urea was added to the raffinate and the second crop of complexes (C_2) formed in the usual manner was also separated. The esters were isolated from both the complexes and the last raffinate as usual. The characteristics of the various fractions obtained in the separation of the mixtures of (1) stearic-linoleic esters and (2) stearic-oleic esters are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Composition of the fractions of esters formed by addition of urea in stages.

Ester fraction	Stearic-linoleic esters (1:1).			Stearic-oleic esters (1:1).		
	Ester in the fraction.	I. V. (Wijs).	Linoleic ester in the fraction.	Ester in the fraction.	I. V. (Wijs).	Oleic ester in the fraction.
Complexes C ₁	44.62%	28.7	16.7%	50.22%	23.0	26.8%
Complexes C ₂	36.35	101.7	59.0	42.10	66.1	77.2
Raffinate	16.53	163.5	94.8	5.18	85.2	99.5

Separation of Esters by Urea-complex formation in dilute solution.—It has been observed before that unsaturated acids form solid urea complexes progressively in increasing amounts as the quantity of methyl alcohol used in their formation is decreased. With a view to^a ascertaining the effect of dilute solution of urea in methyl alcohol on the separation of esters, experiments were conducted with a mixture of stearic and linoleic esters (1:1). Different quantities of 10% urea solution in methyl alcohol were added to 1 g. samples of the above mixture and complexes were formed as usual at 15°. The esters were isolated from the solid complexes. Their quantities and composition are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Separation of the mixture of stearic and linoleic acid esters (1:1) by complex formation in 10% urea solution in methyl alcohol.

No.	Urea soln. added per g. of the ester mixture.	Ester from complexes		
		Amount.	I. V. (Wijs).	Linoleic ester in the fraction.
1	24.6 g.	25.02 %	1.06	0.73%
2	100.5	44.75	2.10	1.80
3	138.7	45.81	2.80	1.65

C O N C L U S I O N

The results of the separation of the components of the mixture of linoleic and stearic acid esters by urea complexes (Table I) are more or less in the similar lines as those of Schlenk and Holman (*loc. cit.*) who carried out the fractionation only in saturated solution of urea in methyl alcohol at 25°. If less urea is employed for complex formation, the amount of unsaturated component in the solid complex fraction decreases, but correspondingly smaller yield of the saturated ester is obtained. Crystallisation of the complexes from methyl alcohol does not reduce the unsaturated component appreciably (Table II). Unsaturated component of sufficient purity is obtained from the raffinate when the urea is added in two stages (Table III), but its amount is only of the order of 5 to 16.5% as against 50% present in the original mixture. A comparison of the results obtained in complex formation with a small quantity of solvent

(Table I, No. 5) and in presence of a larger amount of methyl alcohol (Table IV) is interesting. The separation into saturated and unsaturated constituents is very little in the former case, but methyl stearate of sufficient purity could be obtained from solid complexes in the latter set of experiments where a dilute solution of urea in methyl alcohol (10%) was employed. The recovery of the saturated ester out of solid complexes from a mixture of stearic and linoleic acid ester (1:1) in this case (Table IV), however, does not go above 45% even when 13.8 g. of urea is added per gram of the ester mixture. As expected, the separation is comparatively good when one of the components is of a higher unsaturation.

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